

EDUCATIONAL EQUATIONS: UNPACKING DOUBLE REDUCTION AND FAMILY ENGAGEMENT IN COMPULSORY EDUCATION – A CASE STUDY OF LUOYANG CITY

Maria Teresa Santos Reyes

University of the Cordilleras, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10953077>

Abstract: The "double reduction" policy in China, aimed at alleviating the heavy homework and off-campus training burdens on students in compulsory education, holds paramount importance for the holistic development of minors. This policy has garnered widespread attention from educational stakeholders, parents, and society at large. In 2021, the release of the "Opinions on Further Reducing the Burden of Homework and Off-campus Training for Students Receiving Compulsory Education" marked a pivotal step towards promoting students' comprehensive growth and well-being. Over the past year, Luoyang City has spearheaded initiatives to enhance school quality and off-campus governance, emphasizing collaborative efforts between schools and parents. These endeavors have borne fruit by significantly reducing the homework and off-campus training burdens on students. This accomplishment is attributed to various factors: the education department's improved management mechanisms, stringent controls on the workload of primary and secondary school students, and the comprehensive implementation of after-school services, ensuring accessibility for all students in need. This achievement presents a promising "report card" that showcases the positive impact of proactive measures to mitigate the "double reduction" challenges in compulsory education. The success of these efforts underscores the significance of "double reduction" in nurturing the holistic development of young learners.

Keywords: Double reduction, Compulsory education, Homework burden, Off-campus training
Holistic development

Introduction

"Double reduction" means that the heavy homework burden and off-campus training burden of students in compulsory education in China should be effectively reduced. The implementation of the "double reduction" policy is one of the core concerns of China's compulsory education.^[1] "Double reduction" is of great value and significance to the growth of minors. School administrators, education practitioners, parents and all sectors of society at the stage of compulsory education should attach importance to "double reduction" and actively respond to "double reduction".^[2] In 2021, with the goal "Promoting Students' all-round development and healthy growth", the Opinions on Further Reducing the Burden of Homework and Off-campus Training for Students receiving compulsory education were released.^[3] In the past year, Luoyang City took "overall promotion, focus on key points, home-school co-education, strengthen publicity" as the focus of school quality improvement, and "perfect system and mechanism, focus on supervision and rectification, update parents' ideas, strengthen platform construction" as the focus of off-campus governance, to realize the linkage of "quality improvement in school" and "off-campus governance".^[4] And it effectively reduce the heavy homework burden of students in compulsory education and off-campus training burden, handed over a bright "report card" : first, the education department to

improve the operation management mechanism, publicity system, strictly control the amount of work of primary and secondary school students; Second, we fully implemented after-school services, achieving full coverage of compulsory education schools and providing coverage to all students in need.^[5]

1. Research content

The object of this study is the family members of the compulsory education students in Luoyang Municipal District. This study mainly focuses on the understanding, reaction and influence of the research objects on the "double reduction" policy and the change of family education mode. Through the combination of questionnaire survey and field visit, this study focuses on the reaction of the family members in Luoyang to the "double reduction" policy. The investigation contents include gender, parental title, age, family income, educational background of parents and children. According to the satisfaction scores, the family members' satisfaction with the "double reduction" policy was investigated. Through questionnaire survey, questionnaire scale was designed to investigate the influencing factors, including the change of children's grades, the change of parenting style, parent-child companionship and communication, interest and hobby investment, discipline education investment, leisure time arrangement and other factors.

A quantitative questionnaire survey was conducted on family members in Luoyang, Henan Province to study the family reaction and influence of the "double reduction" of education in Henan Province (including the above four research questions). Using SPSS 22.0 data analysis software, through single sample analysis and correlation analysis, this paper analyzes the reaction and influence of "double reduction" policy on Luoyang city residents. In the questionnaire survey, a total of 461 questionnaires were collected, among which 450 were valid. Through qualitative analysis, interview, face-to-face interview and telephone interview, 40 households in Luoyang urban area were sampled to investigate the response of family members in Luoyang urban area to the "double reduction" policy and the change of family parenting style. Meanwhile, the recorded data were translated and compiled, and the theme was coded by QRS NVivo 8.0, a qualitative research software. Analyze the influence of "double reduction" policy on family education in Luoyang City.

2. Research status

After the network questionnaire survey, 450 valid questionnaire data (n=280) were imported into SPSS 22.0 for data analysis, and the text data and interview materials were transcribed, and qualitative analysis software QRS NVivo 8.0 was imported for coding, node coding and tree map coding. The research findings are as follows.

1) Parents spend more time with their children, and the parent-child relationship is more harmonious
In the online questionnaire of 421 families in Luoyang City, 55.90% of them said that they are more willing to accompany their children and spend significantly longer time with them than before the 'double reduction'. Correspondingly, after the "double reduction", parents' organizations have more time to participate in children's learning and growth, and the activities are more abundant. In the questionnaire survey, the respondents were parents of compulsory education. Surprisingly, among the 610 interviewed parents, 57.05% said that "compared with the 'double reduction', they spend more time with their children", and 47.38% chose "parent-child relationship is better than the 'double reduction'". Correspondingly, after the "double reduction", parents' organizations have more time to participate in children's learning and growth, and the activities are more abundant. Accompany has become a "double" summer high frequency word. Whether it is to play or study, whether it is to fly the dog or the mother is kind and filial, more time to get along with each other, more diversified parent-child interaction, and "double reduction" allows parents to return to the rightful position of family education. And "Learning shouldn't just happen in classrooms and schools. Learning is everyone's way of life throughout their life. In contrast, we should pay more attention to the cultivation of internal quality and the construction of family tradition. Only with stable mentality and education concept can children grow up with fewer twists and turns and take the right path.

2) The number of students participating in off-campus training institutions in disciplines has decreased significantly.

In the survey, the author found that 50.74% of parents were satisfied with the "burden reduction". In the implementation of the "double reduction" work, the Luoyang Municipal government strengthened the "three improvements": to improve the level of homework management, improve the level of after-school service and improve the quality of classroom teaching. The effect of reducing the burden of the school is beginning to show, and the homework burden is obviously reduced. The child's grades have improved markedly.

3) Students' sleep quality is effectively guaranteed and their free time is significantly increased

The survey found that after the implementation of the "double reduction" policy, 49.91% of the students (Figure 3) slept 8-9 hours, and 25.91% slept 9-10 hours. It can be seen that the sleep quality of students was slightly improved. However, at the same time, the "double reduction" policy has reformed various forms of education and training institutions in the society. In the past, students' summer and winter holidays, weekends and various holidays were all arranged by their parents. Out-of-school training institutions can be rectified after the restriction, these time are free out, the children have more and more free time. Educational institutions also want children to make good use of free time, ensure adequate sleep every day. Comply with the law of children's growth, to ensure the physical and mental health of each student.

The extra free time has become a new headache for parents. Children used to spend most of the day in remedial classes, but now they have to stay at home. Parents not only have to take care of their children's food, clothing, housing and transportation, but also have to shoulder the heavy responsibility of helping with homework. However, some parents have limited educational level, which makes it difficult to help junior high school students with their homework. This makes parents very worried, fearing that it will affect their children's academic progress.

4) "Double-minus" policy reduces depression in adolescents and increases anxiety in parents

The study found that in the year after the "double reduction" policy was implemented, depressive symptoms in adolescents decreased by 78.6 percent. This is mainly attributed to the reduction in academic burden from the reduction or even prohibition of homework assignments, the increase in time spent by parents as they switch to home schooling, and the significant reduction in test anxiety from the disallowing of tests or the banning of rankings. The effect of "double reduction" has been initially shown. But what makes parents more anxious is that in the past, their children's grades are not good, so they can choose out-of-school training. Many parents think that they can get returns by paying money, "as long as they take classes, they can improve their grades". With the implementation of the "double reduction" policy, the choice range of off-campus training institutions is shrinking, and more parents who have demand for "make up lessons" can only choose one-to-one tutoring with higher cost, which is not a small pressure on the family economy. The "double reduction" is not just a matter for the education system. Children are related to their parents, and parents are related to the society. Education has always been a major issue related to the national economy and people's livelihood. It is a field highly related to the needs of the country and the people. The whole society should care about education, so that children can improve their ability through their thirst for knowledge, instead of spending a lot of time on "brushing" and enduring high intensity and long-time training. Return to the essence of education, let the children develop morally, intellectually, physically, the United States and labor in an all-round way, build a strong body, tough spirit; Let parents have enough time to devote to family education, so that children can get company and care, and create a harmonious family and social atmosphere.

5) Parents' education mode has shifted from emphasizing knowledge to forging quality

Through the interview, it is found that since the introduction of the "double reduction" policy, parents pay more attention to the development of children's comprehensive quality, and no longer evaluate children on the basis of only points. Children constantly form cognition and construction experience in the interaction with the surrounding environment, things and people. They are active learners, and the learning process is generated and open. It is to understand and apply the new problem situation on the basis of the existing cognitive experience, which not only follows certain universal scientific laws, but also presents strong personalized experience. "Double

reduction" is to liberate children from the single and narrow book learning and get rid of the boring memorization exercises, highlight the role of individual life experience, emotional experience and practical action in learning, and carry forward the value of direct experience to indirect experience, so that children can show their initiative and truly become the master of learning. The family living situation is full of endless, vivid, natural, random and intrinsically related educational opportunities. Parents should deeply understand the rules of children's learning, abandon the excessive strengthening of knowledge and skills, capture children's curiosity and learning interest, create problems and challenges, encourage hands-on and brain experiments, and improve their ability to comprehensively apply the knowledge they have learned to solve complex problems. Realize learning immediacy, interest and usefulness. At the same time, children should be asked to undertake specific tasks in family life and affairs, and forge the necessary quality to adapt to future study and life.

6) "Student achievement is clearly polarized

Studies show that families who focus on improving their children's ability to learn by themselves teach their children by hand, reflect on their situation, learn from their weaknesses in an orderly way, and even continue to learn. Have the ability of self-learning children, in the process of reading will subconsciously accumulate good words good sentence structure, when the brush will take the initiative to touch the rule to find tricks, their drive has been constantly improved, performance has been significantly improved, and those who rely on remedial classes, do not attach importance to the children's results of parents, children's academic performance has significantly declined, the previous children, My children, who usually fill their weekends with private institutes, now have a lot of free time. Some parents take their children to stick to sports, develop interests, practice reading, learning, while some parents take their children to play games, play mobile phones, watch TV.

3. Conclusions and Suggestions

Through quantitative and qualitative research methods, this study comprehensively analyzed the family response and influence of urban families in Luoyang City, Henan Province to the "double reduction" of education. The study found that since the "double reduction" policy in Luoyang, Henan Province, parents accompany their children longer, the parent-child relationship is more harmonious, students' participation in off-campus training institutions in subjects decreased significantly, students' sleep time was guaranteed, which also reduced the depression of teenagers, but at the same time, the polarization of academic performance also increased the anxiety of parents.

First, multi-party coordination to ensure policy implementation. Schools should explore the construction of a new evaluation system for students' comprehensive quality, abandon the study evaluation with ranking nature, and build a training mode of "good health, high emotional intelligence, excellent academic ability", accelerating the construction of the home-school-community collaborative education mechanism, innovating collaborative ways, providing family education guidance, consultation and guidance to parents through online and offline forms, guiding parents to grasp scientific education concepts and methods, and rationally planning the future development direction of children, so that they can maintain a rational attitude towards children's growth expectations, and form a consensus of "reducing the burden". All parties will work together to form synergy in the aspects of "five-point management", deepening education evaluation and reforming education system, constantly strengthen the role of schools as the main front of education, and promote the implementation of "double reduction". The second is to establish the idea of scientific education to relieve the anxiety of family education. Education departments and schools should guide parents to pay more attention to the cultivation of minor children's moral character, scientific exploration spirit and innovative consciousness, as well as the cultivation of good learning habits, behavior habits and living habits. In terms of family education methods, parents should be guided to establish the correct idea of family education, improve the ability of family education, and create a good family environment for the healthy growth of minors. Parents are encouraged to reasonably arrange the time of study, rest, recreation and physical exercise for minors, avoid aggravating their learning burden and prevent them from becoming addicted to the Internet. The third is to establish a good parent-child

relationship in the family, in the high-quality company, let the healthy development of children, really pay attention to the inner growth of children's communication and exchange is the most valuable investment. "Double reduction" relieves children and parents from the endless homework, exercises and tests, and enables parents to observe and empathize with their child's daily emotional feelings in a relaxed state, hold open discussions around the confusion he encounters, and support him to try to solve the problem through reflection. Fourth, we will increase quality education resources and promote balanced compulsory education. We will expand quality educational resources by actively promoting collectivized school running, building and expanding schools, and optimizing existing school districts. We will actively seek financial support from the central and provincial governments, guarantee after-school service funds by means of financial subsidies and service charges, and promote after-school services by means of hiring external teachers, purchasing third-party services and introducing volunteers to further meet students' personalized needs. Strengthen free online learning services at the provincial and municipal level, provide learning resources covering subjects of all grades, and expand the use rate and coverage of high-quality education resources.

This survey also has certain limitations, such as tight survey time and heavy tasks, limited number of respondents and insufficient number of interviewees. Moreover, this survey is mainly conducted in Jianxi District, Luolong District and Xigong District, and lacks a survey of households in all urban areas of Luoyang City, so the conclusions of this study have certain limitations. However, the research group adopts scientific quantitative and qualitative research methods, actively designs questionnaires and interview questions, and adopts scientific methods to actively collate and analyze the collected data. The research conclusions are in line with the methods and procedures of scientific research and have a certain scientific nature.

References

- Zhang Pin, Lin Xiaoshan. "Double Reduction" and "Double Spelling": Parental Anxiety and family Upbringing in the Great Reform of Education Policy [J]. *Social Construction*, 2022-01.
- Dong Hongjun. Home-school Co-parenting under the Background of "Double Reduction" [J]. *China Education Journal*, 2021-12.
- Li Yaning. Double Reduction, Family education should do this [J]. *Family Life Guide*, 2021-11. [4] Wu P. New Challenges and opportunities for family education under the background of "Double Reduction" policy [J]. *Inner Mongolia Education*, 2021-11.
- Zhang Yiming. Perfect Family Education, Escort for "Double Reduction" Policy [J]. *Modern Vocational Education*, 2022-01.